

PARE PRELIMINARY ANALYSIS OF ACARE FLIGHTPATH 2050 ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT GOALS

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ABSTRACT:

European aviation plays a key role in serving society's needs for safe, secure and sustainable mobility in Europe and all over the world. Its impact on the wider European economy is significant and must be sustained. Environmental protection is and will continue to be a key driver for the aviation industry as a whole. Meeting community expectations on aircraft noise, engine emission and fuel/energy consumption has always presented a challenge to aircraft and engine manufacturers and to those involved in airport planning and air traffic management. The paper describes the current points of the EU civil aviation on a way to *FlightPath 2050* Challenge 3 goals, defined in PARE project at mid term stage.

1. INTRODUCTION

Aviation is recognised as one of the top advanced technology sectors in Europe and generates innovation that benefits society at large far beyond its direct operational sphere. It provides close to

twelve million skilled jobs, directly and indirectly, and contributes over 700 billion euros to Europe's gross domestic product [1]. Home to some 400 airlines and nearly 700 airports, European aviation plays a key role in serving society's needs for safe, secure and sustainable mobility in Europe and all over the world. Its impact on the wider European economy is significant and must be sustained.

EU aerospace research towards *Flightpath 2050* goals [2] faces several challenges. Environmental protection is and will continue to be a key driver for the aviation industry as a whole. The challenge with respect to the environment is to reduce continuously the environmental impact in the face of continuing expansion in demand for aviation. This expansion will also put pressure on existing energy supplies. In 2050 technologies and procedures available allow a **75% reduction in CO₂** emissions per passenger kilometre and a **90% reduction in NO_x emissions**. The **perceived noise emission of flying aircraft is reduced by 65%**. These are relative to the capabilities of typical new aircraft in 2000 (Table 1).

Table 1: Comparison of long-term goals for environmental impact factors of aviation between ICAO Policy, EU and USA Research and Development agenda

Environmental impact factor from aviation	ICAO Policy Goals [4]	EU ACARE Goals (FP2050 till 2050)	US FAA and NASA Goals (NSTC2010 [5] and CLEEN II [6] till 2035)
Noise	Limit or reduce the number of people affected by significant aircraft noise	perceived noise emission of flying aircraft is reduced by 65%	52 dB reduction relative to cumulative margin of ICAO/FAA Stage 4 noise limit (a 25-year goal, by enabling N+3 aircraft and engines)
NO _x emissions	Limit or reduce the impact of aviation emissions on local air quality	90% reduction in NO _x emissions	80% reduction in NO _x emissions (for cruise relative to 2005 best in class and for LTO relative to ICAO CAEP/6 standard)
Green-house gas emissions and fuel/energy consumption	Limit or reduce the impact of aviation green-house gas emissions on the global climate: a reduction in net aviation CO₂ emissions of 50% by 2050, relative to 2005 levels	75% reduction in CO₂ emissions per passenger kilometre, relative to typical new aircraft in 2000	60% reduction in Aircraft Fuel/Energy Consumption (CO ₂ emissions per passenger kilometre?) relative to 2000 best in class

ACARE will continue to foster the need to monitor achievements and progress on the SRIA objectives. As an example, in 2015 the ACARE

working group on energy and environment estimated that EU aviation sector had secured an overall 38% reduction in CO₂ per passenger-

kilometre against a goal of 50% reduction goal for 2020. Similarly, technical solutions showed a potential reduction of 37% in perceived noise has been achieved against a goal of 50%, also by 2020. Whilst this represents significant progress, effort must be further strengthened to meet the even more challenging goals for CO₂, noise and NO_x emissions set for 2050 [1].

2. AIR TRAFFIC AND CORRESPONDENT IMPACT ON ENVIRONMENT FORECASTING

In 2017, 1 043 million people in the EU travelled by air, an increase of 7.3 % compared with 2016, and 6,7 % increase in 2018 (6,4 % increase globally) – air travel growth has eased in comparison to the strong upward trend seen in

2017, but still continue to go along Regulation and Growth Forecast (Figure 1). Strong and broad-based traffic growth in 2017 across all market segments finally took European flight totals over the 2008 peak, to 10.6 million. Indeed, even 4% growth in flights in 2017 looks modest compared to almost twice that reported for passengers or passenger-km. European airlines saw traffic rise 5.6% in June 2019 compared to June 2018, with overall estimated flight growth for 2019 at 1.1% [3]. Capacity climbed 4.5% and load factor rose 1% percentage point to 87.9%. Current growth is certainly supported by strong demand. This growth has brought traffic back to the most-likely scenario from the 2013 forecast (after double-dip decline in 2008 – Figure 1).

Figure 1: In 2017-2019, strong growth saw traffic back on the most-likely scenario from the 2013 forecast, modified from [7]

All such forecasts in flight traffic, and accordingly - airport operational capacity limitations, enroute congestion provide the conditions for a growth of impact of aviation on environment. The Challenges of Growth 2018 environment report [6] describes the background and impact in more detail. It also begins to address some of the adaptation measures that are available.

The local environment agenda for aviation is driven largely by noise and occasionally by local air quality impacts, whereas the national and international agenda is primarily focussed on climate change and carbon dioxide emissions. In carrying out its responsibilities, ICAO and its Member States will strive to limit or reduce these dominant and prioritised impact factors (Table 1). Meeting community expectations on aircraft noise, engine emission and fuel/energy consumption has always presented a challenge to aircraft and

engine manufacturers and to those involved in airport planning and air traffic management. To achieve these targets, all (governmental and industrial) stakeholders agreed to closely work together along a four-pillar strategy:

- *Improved technology*, including the deployment of sustainable low-carbon fuels;
- *More efficient aircraft operations*;
- *Infrastructure improvements*, including modernized air traffic management systems;
- *Actions within the aviation sector to adapt and develop resilience* to the current and future impacts of climate change
- *A single global market-based measure*, to fill the remaining emissions gap.

Continued efforts may stabilize noise exposure by 2035-2040, but it will continue to be a key

challenge. Noise exposure has stabilized over the past ten years. The total population inside the L_{den} and L_{night} contours decreased by only 2% (L_{den}) and 1% (L_{night}) between 2005 and 2014, to reach

2.52 and 1.18 million people respectively in 2014 (EUA 2016), and 2.58 and 0.98 million people respectively in 2017 (Figure 2, [8]).

Figure 2: Fleet renewal could stabilise average noise levels at today's 47 major airports by 2030 [8]

In 2012, aviation represented 13% of all EU transport CO_2 emissions and 3% of the total EU CO_2 emissions. EU aviation specifically represents 22% of global aviation's CO_2 emissions. The EU plays a leading role in international efforts to limit climate change, and increased its climate finance contributions to €20.2 billion in 2016. This is backed up by a

legally binding commitment and legal framework at EU level to reduce greenhouse gas emissions, increase the use of renewable energy and improve energy efficiency [8]. Due to fleet renewal, emissions of CO_2 , NO_x , HC, CO and PM have been relatively stable between 2005 and 2014 (Figure 3).

a)

b)

Figure 3: emissions are steadily increasing again since 2013: a) CO₂, b) NO_x will increase further, but advanced engine combustor technology could help curb their growth after 2030 [8]

However, nvPM emissions are expected to increase over the next twenty years if engine technology remains as it is today (it is expected *+25% growth till 2040*). The ‘climate and energy’ targets for 2020, which the EU is on track to meet, and 2030 are shown below [8]:

2020

- 20% cut in greenhouse gas emission (from 1990 levels)
- 20% of EU energy from renewables
- 20% improvement in energy efficiency

2030

- At least 40% cut in greenhouse gas emission (from 1990 levels)
- 32% of EU energy from renewables, with an upwards revision clause by 2023
- 32.5% improvement in energy efficiency, with an upwards revision clause by 2023
- The EU has also agreed on a ‘2050 low carbon economy’ roadmap that suggests the following targets:

- 60% cut in greenhouse gas emission by **2040** (from 1990 levels)

- 80% cut in greenhouse gas emission by **2050** (from 1990 levels), including a 60% reduction in transport emissions.

It is clear from available studies that these goals cannot all be achieved using evolutions of currently available technologies. Research and innovation for evolutionary aircraft development will drive progress in environmental performance to be on track towards the FP2050 goals. Changes will be introduced in new aircraft or by retrofit into the growing civil aerospace fleet. It is also essential that such technology roadmap and its implementation must continue to receive support through government policy and that it remains a priority for European society (Figure 4).

Figure 4: The goals and action areas for Challenge 3 of the ACARE perspectives

To achieve the 2050 goals, step changes in aircraft configuration and operation (including alternative energy sources) will be required - currently envisaged evolutions will not be sufficient [1]. For example, noise and emissions reductions can be achieved only if sufficient efforts are made for new technologies to mature; the transition from technology availability to technology uptake in a product or system is influenced by many factors; besides technology maturation, certification, sustainability and cost-effectiveness. There are also factors of a non-technological nature such as market expectations, new products or improvements being developed. Towards 2050, the forecast growth in the aviation industry will drive the need to deliver revolutionary technology solutions at an increasing rate and secure the path to sustainable energy supplies that can displace today's fossil

fuels to mitigate fully the potential impact on the atmosphere.

3. TECHNOLOGY READINESS LEVEL ASSESSMENT

One of the biggest challenges in managing technology is to properly choose which technologies to invest in and to know when technologies are ready or mature enough to be considered for a particular system/product. There are not plenty of metrics and tools developed to measure how ready a technology is. The most universally accepted methodology for assessing the upward slope of this curve is the *Technology Readiness Level (TRL) scale* - a systematic, metric-based assessment of how far technology development has progressed. TRLs are used to quantify the technology maturity status of an element intended to be used in a mission in accordance with Standard ISO 16290, 2013. The timeframe to 2050 leaves scope to mature what is now low TRL basic research to promising high TRL demonstrations and feasible solutions to meet aviation targets.

3.1. Reduction of Noise and Emissions

Flightpath 2050 goal 9: "In 2050 technologies and procedures available allow a 75% reduction in CO₂ emissions per passenger km and a 90% reduction in NO_x emissions. The perceived noise of flying aircraft is reduced by 65%. These are relative to the capabilities of typical new aircraft in 2000". This goal covers noise and emissions. The distinction is made between engine and aerodynamic noise and local and global emissions.

Unfortunately, aircraft have a large number of noise sources. The major sources of engine noise are the fan and jet, and to a lesser extent, the compressors, combustor, turbine and bleeds (which may actually dominate at certain times during flight). Airframe noise is generated by the airflow surrounding the moving plane. The main sources are the discontinuities of the aircraft structure, such as high-lift devices (HLD), landing gear wheels (when extended), and trailing edges which lead to speed shearing (aircraft speed versus still air).

Figure 5: Sources of acoustic emission during: a) takeoff; b) landing (Leylekian, L., Lebrun, M., Lempereur, P. 2014).

A further source of noise arises from the interaction of the engines exhaust jet with the airframe. As a general rule, engine sources dominate on take-off while airframe noise dominates on approach ((Figure 5)).

There is potential for reducing noise by way of better component design and incremental improvements in existing technology, but it is not appropriate to detail all the possibilities here (Table 2 is for illustrative examples).

Instead, we highlight where new technological improvement is likely, and cases where an improvement in aircraft efficiency and gaseous emissions creates a new noise risk that will need to be addressed. However, they can be broadly classified as engine noise sources and airframe noise sources.

The major contributor to the reduction of engine noise has been the increase in the by-pass ratio of turbofan engines, which also decreases fuel consumption, leading both to lower emissions and more favorable economics. The range of liners employed to attenuate noise will be significant in the near term. Specifically, lip liners (where the intake liner is extended around the lip of the nacelle intake) are feasible now that the problem of integrating them with the de-icing system has been overcome. Modern ceramics and improved manufacturing have made core exhaust liners possible, but the problem of high temperatures and a highly curved geometry must still be solved. Equally, ALM allows for varying the depth of nacelle liners to obtain a distribution of acoustic

impedance that can be optimised for maximum attenuation (Nark et al., 2016) or the use of

radically new liner design (Koch et al., 2017).

Table 2. Examples of potential noise reduction through component improvements. (Based on data given in (CAEP/9 Meeting, 2013))

Component	Technology	Estimated dB Reduction on component level	Timescale	Notes
Fan	Rotor Sweep and Stator sweep and lean	2dB	Near term	
	Variable Area Nozzle	2dB	Near term	Complexity and weight issues
	Liner improvements	2--4dB	Near term	Manufacture & repair technologies. Integration with other systems such as de-icing.
	Active stators	Up to 8dB	Near/Long term	Highly complex. Weight & structural integrity issues.
	Active blade control	Up to 20dB	Near/Long term	
Jet	Chevrans	1 -- 3dB on TO	Near term	Potential fuel burn penalty
	Fluid injection/microjets/excitation	1--3dB	Near/Long term	Highly complex.
Landing Gear	Fairings	Up to 3dB	Near term	Weight penalty. Maintenance access.
	Low noise design	Up to 5dB	Near/Long term	
	Flow control	1dB	Near/Long term	Weight penalty.
High Lift Devices	Slat & track treatment	Up to 5dB	Near term	Potential for increased drag => fuel penalty
	Flap side edge treatment	Up to 5dB	Near term	Potential for increased drag => fuel penalty
	Low noise design	Up to 5dB	Near/Long term	Potential for increased drag => fuel penalty
Core	Hot liners	2--4dB	Near term	

An approach by consensus based on expert's judgement, assessment of the TRL situation and results from the technology evaluation exercises has then been used to perform the 2015 progress assessment, coming up with updated progress achievement figures and formulating associated recommendations for future research. Recommended Phased Approach to meet ACARE Noise Goal #9 includes analysis of

expected advances on noise reduction with Noise Reduction Technology 1 (NRT1) and NRT2, as well as the Noise Abatement Procedure. For example, NYSERDA TRL Calculator results for analysis and assessment of **ACARE Challenge 3 Goal 9** "Reduction of Noise and Emissions" achievements at 1st stage of the researches on PARE Project are shown in Figure 6 grounding on the results of the 1st year PARE report.

Category	Answer
Technology	Preliminary testing of technology components has begun, and technical feasibility has been established in a laboratory environment
Product Development	Demonstration of a full scale product/system prototype has been completed in the intended application(s)
Product Definition/Design	The product/system has been scaled from laboratory to pilot scale and issues that may affect achieving full scale have been identified
Competitive Landscape	Competitive analysis to illustrate unique features and advantages of the product/system compared to competitive products/systems has been completed
Team	Balanced team with technical and business development/commercialization experience running the company with assistance from outside advisors/mentors
Go-To-Market	Market and customer/partner needs and how those translate to product requirements have been defined, and initial relationships have been developed with key stakeholders across the value chain
Manufacturing/Supply Chain	Manufacturing process qualifications (e.g. QC/QA) have been defined and are in progress

Figure 6: NYSERDA TRL Calculator results for analysis and assessment of ACARE Challenge 3 Goal 9 "Reduction of Noise and Emissions"

Aviation emissions of CO₂ and NO_x are produced by aircraft, support vehicles and ground transportation dominantly. The emissions from these sources fall into two categories: emissions that cause deterioration in local air quality (LAQ) and emissions that cause climate change. Current

and future technological developments to achieve the challenging ACARE 2050 CO₂ goal are essential to mitigate substantially the increase of aviation CO₂, with realistic traffic growth assumption (Figure 7).

Figure 7: Global aviation CO₂ forecast with ACARE assumption [9]

A large part of the effort of the last decade was supported within EU Clean Sky, and within other European projects like LEMCOTEC, ENOVAL and E-BREAK. To achieve the 2050 goals, step changes in aircraft configuration and operation (including alternative energy sources) will be required - currently envisaged evolutions will not be sufficient [3]. ACARE runs three research

projects to achieve these goals: *X-Noise EV*, which relates to aviation noise research, *Forum AE*, which relates to emissions research, and *Core-Jet Fuel*, which relates to alternative aviation fuels.

A new assessment was performed against ACARE CO₂ and NO_x goals and is summarized in the following Table 3.

Table 3:FORUM-AE assessment against ACARE emissions goals [10]

	Reference 2000	ACARE 2020 Goals (at TRL6)		ACARE 2050 Goals (at TRL6)	
		High Level	detailed (SRA)	High Level	detailed (SRIA)
CO ₂	Representative technology of aircraft & engine with 2000 EIS, & representative 2000 ATM	"-50% per pass km"	aircraft: -20% to -25% engine: -15% to -20% ATM: -5% to -10%	"-75% per pass km"	aircraft & engine: -68% ATM: -12% Other: -12%
NO _x (LTO)		"-80%"	engine: -60% CAEP6 ; complement achieved by aircraft + ATM	"-90%"	engine: -75% CAEP6 ; complement achieved by aircraft + ATM
NO _x (Cruise)		"-80%"	Achieved through -50% Fuel Burn & -60% cruise EINO _x reduction	"-90%"	Achieved through -75% Fuel Burn & further cruise EINO _x reduction
Other emissions		"damaging emissions reduced"	emissions qualitatively reduced (particles, CO, UHC) and better understanding of impacts	"emissions-free taxiing" + qualitative reduction	knowledge of emissions (particles, VOC) and better understanding of impacts

Although, there is no ACARE objective related to ultrafine particles, this is now a key environmental and regulatory concern, which requires appropriate mitigation solutions (combustor technology and fuel composition).

As example, CO₂ Road-Map (Figure 8) demonstrates the potential to accommodate

significant aviation growth to 2050 without a substantial increase in CO₂ emissions, through a better than doubling of carbon efficiency, namely in UK [8]. Through the adoption of newer, more efficient aircraft, sustainable fuels and better air traffic management and operational procedures, the aviation industry in the UK and in total EU will

be able to accommodate significant growth through to 2050, including the effect of additional runway capacity in the East European States (for

EU region), without a substantial increase in CO₂ emissions.

Figure 8: The goals and action areas for Challenge 3 of the ACARE perspectives [13].

4. AIRCRAFT ELECTRIFICATION NOWADAYS AND IN FUTURE

Stepwise development to meet environmental targets in aviation sector – evolutionary and revolutionary technology solutions to be researched and implemented – provides a necessity to formulate midterm and long term goals, especially driven by climate change impact of aviation. For example a concept of More Electric Aircraft (MEA) covers a number of technologies to be introduced in aircraft control in flight during nearest decades (midterm goals for emission reduction and energy supply). Full Electric Aircraft (EA) concept is considered like a subject of deep concern for the last decade (long term goals) in progress to 2050 achievements. Complexity of the Challenge 3 towards *FlightPath 2050* creates the conditions when/where new evolutionary and revolutionary technology achievements are expected in all spheres of aviation sector – aircraft design and manufacturing, their operation and maintenance,

including airport and ATC infrastructure and procedures.

New technologies will bring change, challenge and opportunity, too. This will comprise harnessing the benefits of changes to technology embedded onto aircraft, including the coming revolution in full-electric (use batteries as the only source of propulsion power on the aircraft) or hybrid electric power for aircraft and other disruptors like the possibilities of urban air mobility vehicles. Electrification of aircraft has the potential to revolutionize the aerospace and aviation industries. Up to date a number of new programmes were launched for the four types of aircraft – General Aviation (GA)/Recreational Aircraft, Urban Air Taxis (vertical take-off and landing aircraft), Regional/Business Aircraft and Large Commercial Aircraft (LCA). Most of them target an entry-in-service date between 2020-2030, although some are already commercially available. The design and usage optimization of electric propulsion architectures over a range of aircraft designs and series of missions is complex (Figure 9).

Figure 9: Trends of possible aircraft hybrid architectures at different installed power, from [11]

Electrical propulsion is finally on the map: almost 100 electrically propelled aircraft are already in development globally. Most developments are currently working on general aviation or urban air taxi architectures. Given the current state of technological advancement, this is unsurprising as these smaller architectures require less total power and are less limited by constraints such as battery and motor gravimetric densities. Considering a time span up to 2035, meaning +20 years in Figure 9, we can see how full electric power could be employed only in general aviation and in some commuter or UAV applications, while

partially electric propulsion would be needed to power commuters and regional propeller-driven airplanes. Turbofan aircraft would at most benefit from assisted electric power, provided that a trade-off could be made between engine mass increase and fuel consumption, noise and pollutant emissions decrease; only more electric aircraft tendency is thus expected. Moving to a larger time span, up to 2050 (+35 years), we can expect to have advanced enough batteries to grant high performance to enable full electric power sources even to standard 200-300 PAX airliners, Figure 9.

Figure 10: Fuel burn reduction expectation with respect to year 2000 [12]

This possibility to extend this technology to large aircraft by 2050 is affected by heavy uncertainty and requires large improvements in terms of power-to-weight ratio of electric motors and

electro-mechanical conversion, cooling systems, wiring and, of course, on batteries. Concerning fuel burn reduction, one can observe a potential trend for commercial aircraft, Figure 10. Taking year 2000 as a reference, as

considered by Flightpath 2050 program, it can be expected an improvement due to hybrid electro-mobility starting around 2025, with fuel saving around 25-30% due to advanced turbofan studies, while further improvements are subjected to large uncertainties.

4.1. Emissions Free Taxying at Airports

More than 200 members of ACI Europe, the trade association for European airports, have committed to produce net zero carbon emissions by 2050. The taxiing of aircraft on engine power and the use of auxiliary power units (APU) on the ground can be significant contributors to emissions at airports and also generate noise. UK cross-industry group Sustainable Aviation found that 30% of total CO₂ emissions at Heathrow Airport came from aircraft taxiing and the use of auxiliary power units (APUs). Savings of 100,000 tonnes of CO₂ per year have been calculated at Heathrow from reduced engine taxiing and APU substitution. On a global level, IATA has estimated a CO₂ savings potential in the order of 6 million tonnes annually. The most obvious way to achieve goal 10 is to use electric towing vehicles. There are technical aspects like ensuring compatibility of towing brackets and sufficient traction power. Also infrastructure aspects with recharging facilities for a fleet of electric towing vehicles.

The current preferred battery technologies for ground movements at the airport or on the airfield and in the aircraft itself are the lead – acid and the nickel – cadmium (Ni - Cd) batteries. However, since these batteries are technically exhausted, no significant improvement in terms of energy density, cycle life, calendar life, etc. is expected; There is a shift to lithium – ion (li - ion) technology in the aviation industry, being that li - ion chemistry offers a large variety of materials and cell architectures, which enables the possibility to design high - power as well as high - energy systems.

In general, regarding li – ion batteries, an increase in the energy density, with state-of-the-art chemistry, could be mainly achieved by optimizing the form factor and the cell production process. Nevertheless, even if the current chemistry has proven itself, efforts are still to be made to increase the energy density as well as other key performance parameters to meet future requirements.

5. DESIGN AND MANUFACTURE BEARING IN MIND RECYCLING

Flightpath 2050 goal 11: Air vehicles are designed and manufactured to be recyclable. Recycling of aircraft parts depends mostly on the materials used and also on the fabrication process. The choice of materials for an aircraft is subject to a considerable set of constraints related to performance, weight, availability, cost, ease of

manufacture and maintenance, durability and resistance to hostile environments. Adding the recycling ability is an additional constraint which can bring benefits in several of other areas; it may require consideration of materials not previously used in the aerospace industry and take advantage in the major progress made synthesizing new substances with tailor-made properties (graphene).

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Recent technological advances in the field of power electronics, fault-tolerant architecture, electro-hydrostatic actuators, flight control systems, high density electric motors, power generation and conversion systems have ushered the era of the MEA. A small size, high energy density (more than 100 watt-hour per kilogram (Wh/kg)) battery is the need of the aircraft industry as a 10 kg decrease in the weight of aircraft will result in the savings of 17,000 tons of fuel and 54,000 tons of carbon dioxide emission per year for all air traffic worldwide. The reduction in battery weight is also profitable in terms of cost. The life duration of an aircraft battery depends on various factors such as number of operating hours, ambient temperature, start frequency and on-board charge. It is therefore difficult to determine in advance how long the expected life of a battery will be in the real situation.

It is recommended that a comprehensive assessment of materials used in aircraft production is made and that recyclable alternatives and related issues of availability, ease of use, certification, maintenance and cost are assessed.

6. SUSTAINABLE ALTERNATIVE FUEL SOURCES

Flightpath 2050 goal 12: Europe is established as a centre of excellence for sustainable

alternative fuels, including those for aviation, based on a strong European energy policy.

The supply of fuel alternative to kerosene is subject to major efforts by large consumers like the U.S. Air Force. The consumer base is more diversified in the airline industry but it is no less important due to the large number of flight hours. Although airlines have been willing to test new fuels a coordinated effort must be done far upstream to: (i) consider a variety of sources of fuel, that do not interfere with food production and whose environmental impact is neutral or positive (waste disposal); (ii) establish the technical feasibility to meet all applicable quality and safety standards and certification requirements; (iii) assess the economic and environmental feasibility of large-scale sustained production, distribution and use.

For example hydrogen is a clean fuel that produces only water vapour by combustion; however the quantities produced and altitudes should be considered as for contrails. Hydrogen has a low volume power density and requires cryogenic conditions; water is an abundant source of hydrogen but its separation by hydrolysis is energy consuming. At the opposite extreme some algae have high yields per unit area of culture; the full processing chain up to flight grade fuel needs to be considered. In between other options exist, making multiple sources of aviation fuel all the more desirable.

The use of the biofuel has been tested in two series of flights. The first series of 18 long haul flights from Amsterdam to Aruba, on an Airbus A330-200 (carrying around 4,500 passengers informed about the project) was performed using biojet fuel blend in one engine to compare the performance of the two engines. No significant performance differences were noted, but that the water accumulated in the tanks during flights can be lowered using the synthetic fuel, reducing the maintenance frequency and costs. The second series of 80 short haul flights, from Oslo to Amsterdam, on an Embraer E190, carrying about 8,000 passengers, using the camelina biojet blend in both engines, confirmed the no detrimental effects on operation with similar or slightly better fuel consumption and, no variation in fuel gauging systems. The flight series were complemented with a series of lab based emission measurements using a testbed Auxiliary Power Unit (APU). APU emissions tests were completed for the two ITAKA fuel batches and baselined against a standard fossil Jet fuel: performance parameters were as expected quite similar, fuel consumption decrease up to 1% (saving fuel and CO₂ emissions), and the emitted particulate matter (PM) was decreased up to a 50% for a 50:50 fuel blend. PM emissions are a major air quality concern that are linked with a significant number of premature deaths across Europe. High

paraffinic fuels such as HEFA biojet could significantly help to reduce the impact of this pollutant in the vicinity of airports. The information obtained has been supplied to the International Civil Aviation Organization for the development of future standards for aircraft engines.

ACARE also runs the research project entitled Coordinating research and innovation of Jet and other sustainable aviation Fuel (Core – JetFuel). European aviation specifically must guarantee that, in 2050. It is recommended that a comparative study of potential alternative fuels, their availability in the required large quantities and the feasibility and cost of large - scale production, distribution and use is performed.

7. ATMOSPHERIC RESEARCH, WEATHER AND THE ENVIRONMENT

Flightpath 2050 goal 13: Europe is at the forefront of atmospheric research and takes the lead in the formulation of a prioritized environmental protection plan and the establishment of global environmental standards. Atmospheric hazards have been a safety concern throughout the history of aviation and are addressed in the ACARE goal 15. A better modelling and understanding of atmospheric phenomena can reduce disturbances of air traffic management (ACARE goal 5) and allow an increase of runway capacity at airports (ACARE goal 1). As major users of the airspace aviation can contribute to the monitoring of the atmosphere and to the establishment and implementation of global environmental standards. The monitoring of the atmosphere is performed by a vast array of earth and satellite sensors, plus specialized weather aircraft like those used by NOAA (National Oceanographic and Atmospheric Administration in the US) to fly through tropical storms and collect in-situ atmospheric data. The data transmission capabilities of airliners in modern ATM systems could be used not only for traffic proposes but also to collect atmospheric data in support of environmental standards and policies. It is in interest of airlines to preserve their flight environment and if appropriate some of the millions of flight around the world could be a source of in-situ measurement and monitoring.

There are several methods to monitor the atmosphere, such as: routine ground – based measurements (made by ground – based sensors – land based and buoys); systematic aircraft measurements (made by aircraft and balloons); and satellite measurements (made by space – borne sensors).

Changes to temperature, precipitation, and storm patterns are all expected in the near-term, certainly by 2030. The impacts of sea level rise are more gradual and not expected until later in

the century. However, more frequent and intense storm surges will have an earlier impact on European aviation, reducing capacity and increasing delay.

Currently, there are several European initiatives and projects that have as main objective monitoring the atmosphere through satellite and airborne instrumentation, which are:

- Copernicus project, previously known as the Global Monitoring for Environment and Security (GMES);
- Constellation Observing System for Meteorology, Ionosphere and Climate (COSMIC) project;
- Advanced Satellite Aviation Weather Products (ASAP) initiative;
- European Organisation for the Exploitation of Meteorological Satellites (EUMESAT); In – service Aircraft for a Global Observing System (IAGOS) project.

It is recommended that regular airliner flights are used to collect in-situ atmospheric data, which should further be processed to have near real - time knowledge of conditions along flight routes. This data could be supplemented by drones – unmanned aircraft systems (UAS) - specifically designed to fly in more remote regions of the atmosphere.

8. CONCLUSION

In conclusions there are few current recommendations are formulated for *FlightPath 2050* Challenge 3 Goals: 1) Support a broad research *effort to reduce aircraft noise* (a) at the source (b) through operating procedures and (c) taking into account psychoacoustic effects; 2) Besides struggling with short term solutions to an increasingly pressing *noise problem* a modest effort should be made towards long-term definitive solution: aircraft in audible outside airport boundaries; 3) To formulate a set of *trade-offs* between (a) different types of emissions (CO₂, NO_x, PM and water vapor) in (b) *local airports and global cruise flights*; 4) Besides struggling with short-term emissions problems put a modest effort towards a long-term definitive solution: the hydrogen powered and *electric powered aircraft* are among the possible solutions.

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